

A second series of experiments was carried out in which the concentration of EMK was constant, while that of HTTA was varied over a wide range of concentrations. The plots of the logarithm of the distribution ratio, q , against $[\text{HTTA}]_{org}$, gave a family of straight lines of slope 2.0, indicating that only two HTTA molecules participate in the complexing reaction and free HTTA molecules are not attached to the extracted species since the number of protons liberated is equal to the number of HTTA molecules.

The values of $\log q$ plotted against $\log [\text{EMK}]_{org}$ for various fixed values of $[\text{HTTA}]_{org}$, resulted a family of curves which could be well represented by lines of integral slope 1 at low EMK concentrations, and of slope 2 at higher concentrations of the ketone. The compositions of the extracted species are thus $\text{Co}(\text{TTA})_2 \cdot \text{EMK}$ and $\text{Co}(\text{TTA})_2 \cdot 2\text{EMK}$ respectively.

The dependence of the distribution ratio on the concentrations of the extractant and the hydrogen ion activity indicates that the overall reaction for the extraction process corresponds to $\text{M}^{2+} + 2\text{HTTA}_{org} + 2\text{EMK}_{org} \rightleftharpoons \text{M}(\text{TTA})_2 \cdot (\text{EMK})_{2org} + 2\text{H}^+$

The value of (mixed) extraction constant ($\log K$) obtained for the synergic extraction of cobalt (II) by mixtures of HTTA and EMK in benzene was -6.8 at 30° , which is near the values of extraction constants for other oxygen-containing solvent systems reported earlier^{5,6}. For comparison among alcohol, ketone and ether systems the corresponding values quoted for butyl glycol (BG) and isopropylether (IPE) are -4.0 and -7.4 respectively. It has been reported by various workers¹⁰ that the solubility of the chelate is affected by the basicity of the solvent, its electron donating ability and the possibility of the metal ion maintaining its coordination number. In the case of alcohols, their particular extractive behaviour is caused by the amphoteric nature of the hydroxyl group, similar to that of water, showing both donor and acceptor properties. This characteristic of alcohol affects their solvating capacity which in turn is the major parameter governing the solubility of cobalt complex in, and their extractability into, them. But in the case of EMK and IPE which lack hydrogen, there is no possibility of hydrogen bond formation, and only available source for coordination is through their basic oxygen. Moreover, the physico-chemical properties of IPE, such as dielectric constant ($=3.88$) and dipole moment, are closer to those of inert solvents than to those of other polar solvents like EMK ($=18.5$) and BG ($=30.0$). Hence the possibility of adduct formation with cobalt-TTA chelate is less favourable in IPE as compared to BG and EMK. Thus the order of increasing extractibility of Co-TTA chelate by these solvents can be written as $\text{BG} > \text{EMK} > \text{IPE}$. This is in the order expected from the dielectric constants and the donor properties of these solvents.

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Spectrophotometric Study of Lanthanum-2-Hydroxy-1,4-Naphthoquinone (Lawson) Complex

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SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC investigations indicate the formation of 1:3 chelate, wine red in colour, between La^{3+} and 2-hydroxy-1, 4-naphthoquinone in alcoholic solution.

Survey of literature reveals that 2-Hydroxy-1, 4-naphthoquinone (lawsone) has found its application in qualitative and quantitative estimations of various metals. But no interaction of lanthanum with lawsone has been studied. Recently we have studied and established structures of chelate of lawsone with various metals¹. In the present communication the composition, nature of structure, stability constant of La^{3+} . Lawson chelate is reported.

Experimental

Standard solutions of lawsone (K. K. Laboratories, INC., Plainview, New York, A. R.) and lanthanum nitrate (Rare Earth. Ltd. Udog. Mandel, Kerala) were prepared by dissolving the respective compound in double distilled ethyl alcohol (rectified).

Baush and Lomb spectronic-20 spectrophotometer for absorbance measurements and Perkin-Elmer infra cord spectrophotometer for infra red spectra were used.

Results and Discussion

It has been observed that the order of addition of reactants had no appreciable effect on absorbance.

To find the nature of the chelate formed Vosburg and Cooper² method was used. It is found that only one chelate is formed under conditions of study.

The composition of the chelate, 1:3 was established by the method of job's continuous variation³, molar ratio method⁴ and slope ratio method⁵ at 460 nm.

The stability constant calculated from the Job's continuous variation method is 8.2×10^{10} .

I. R. spectra of the complex in solid state has been taken. The lowering of O-H stretch of the ligand in the complex shows a strong hydrogen-bonding in the ligand. The O-H band at 3125 cm^{-1} in the ligand is shifted to 2985 cm^{-1} in the complex. The lowering of C=O stretch of the ligand in the complex indicates

that coordination of lawsone is through carbonyl oxygen. The carbonyl band at 1650 cm^{-1} in lawsone is shifted to 1539 cm^{-1} .

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